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Uwak, U. E. & Ebong, V. E.

Power and National Interest in Nigerian Foreign Policy (2015-2022)

¹Uwak, U. E., PhD & ²Ebong, V. E., PhD

^{1&2}Department of Political Science and Public Administration, University of Uyo, Uyo

¹08032131102; ²07067291538

¹ukouwak@uniuyo.edu.ng; ²victorebong80@gmail.com

Abstract

Nigeria's foreign policy can be traced to the country's existence. These periods were the colonial and post-colonial periods. The colonial period between 1914 and 1960 is when the entity called Nigeria came into existence as a united nation, even though the country was still under the British colonial rule. The post-colonial period was basically from independence in 1960 till date. The study paid critical attention to the post-colonial period of Nigeria's foreign policy since it can be rightly said that Nigeria, as a sovereign state, started having her national interests from this period. The post-colonial period saw the formation of indigenous foreign policy, which was truly called and referred to as Nigerian foreign policy. The study further examined the evolution of Nigeria's foreign policy before independence and reviewed the country's foreign policy since independence in 1960. Also, the study reviewed the principles and objectives of Nigeria's foreign policy, the determinants of Nigeria's foreign policy, and the challenges of Nigeria's foreign policy. To give the study a scientific basis, the theory of realism as articulated by the works of Thucydides, Nicollo Machiavelli, Hans Morgenthau, and others was considered appropriate for examining the subject matter under study. It was recommended, among others, that there is a need for Nigeria to adopt a sound economic policy as a fundamental prerequisite for conducting effective foreign policy since all foreign policies spring from the economic base of a state.

Keywords: Foreign policy, National interest and Power

Introduction

In every region of the world, pivotal powers take the lead. Such powers possess the geo-strategic advantage to determine the direction of events and actions and shape

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arrangements regionally and continentally, etc. They adopt different strategies, from diplomacy (economic and public) (Sevin, 2015), security, economy, aid and assistance, grants, etc., in their relationships and interactions, and they also have a critical say on issues relating to the development and peace of the region. Such powers played critical roles in establishing development and peace in the region and in establishing important organisations like NATO, the European Union (EU), the United Nations Organisation (UN), etc. (Dokubo and Oluwwadare, 2011). Such was Nigeria's role after independence from British control in October 1960.

Geographically located in the Gulf of Guinea, West African sub-region, Nigeria is the tenth largest country in Africa, with a landmass of 924,000 square kilometres (Africa Economic Outlook, 2003; Country Reports, 2017) and an 853km long coastline (Abdul and Ibrahim, 2013). In addition to crude oil, Nigeria has about thirty-three other varieties of solid mineral deposits that, when fully utilised, will make Nigeria the leading economy in Africa.

Despite a smooth independence, the Nigerian state was left with a seemingly weak and dependent economy, given the many years of colonial dominance and exploitation, and without a real legacy for economic development or scientific and technological takeoff (Mbakwe and Chukwu, 2016). Nations across the globe adopted a modernization approach to development to achieve social and economic changes in the postcolonial world. Developed states adopted the theory of *pushing* developing states and former colonies to economic growth (Jiafeng, 2009:73).

This was not the scenario in Africa, as many of the colonial powers adopted different strategies from colonies. It was in this weak state that Sir Abubakar Belewa declared that “Nigeria's Africa, Africa's Nigeria”, meaning that Nigeria is taking responsibility to support Africa, making Africa's liberation and unity the centre of Nigeria's foreign policy and development initiatives. Nigeria possessed the needed resources, which placed her in a position to fill the identified gaps in other black states.

Indirectly, Nigeria took up the crucial leadership role as a continental hegemon to fight colonialism, racism, and apartheid (Emenike, 2007; Ezeolisa, 2015), combat conflict, and assist weak African nations to build stronger institutions and promote African unity. Nigeria's foreign policy was therefore interpreted along these lines, under different governments. It has therefore become imperative to navigate the political,

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economic, and social landscape of Nigeria over the years to comprehend the nature and content of her foreign affairs (Mbakwu and Chukwu, 2016).

Conceptual Clarification

Concepts of Foreign Policy

Foreign policy, like any other social science concept, has defied one universally acceptable definition. Hence, scholars have made various attempts to come up with the most acceptable definition of the concept. Accordingly, Akpotor (2005:159) sees it as a well-documented programme of action with institutionally designated officials who seek to manipulate the international environment with the aim of achieving certain objectives. According to Dauda (2002), foreign policy is that segment of public policy of a state that is concerned with state relations with other states and international organisations. Nnoli (1978) sees foreign policy as a nation's reactions to the external environment involving the organisation as well as the changes in the international environment. From Nnoli's definition, it is assumed that all international contact is related to foreign policy. However, this is not true; not all international contact can really be associated with foreign policy. This is because foreign policy covers only such activities that are sponsored, supported, or known by the government. It is therefore clear that actions that are international in character but that are conducted without the knowledge of the government cannot be classified under foreign policy (Obi 2006:18). To Akinboye (2007), foreign policy is a type of policy that transcends the boundaries of a given state. Accordingly, policy is that kind of action a state embarks upon in its interaction with other member states in the international environment. However, in spite of the defiant definition of foreign policy, there is a common recognition that foreign policy is about national goals and the means and ways of propagating and achieving them (Dauda 2002:2).

The Nature of Foreign Policy

The nature of foreign policy can be summarised as follows:

- i. Foreign policy must have a sound domestic base. In other words, there must be resources that would enhance the policy to achieve its objectives.

- ii. Foreign policy is not only the preserves of government. In contemporary international system, many multinational organisations exist to promote businesses or cultural values. These organisations do articulate policies that are intended to influence the international system. Policies of these organisations sometimes influence foreign policy of states. To pursue these objectives, states in the international system irrespective of their political orientation and levels of economic development use various methods and instruments of foreign policy to influence and sometimes, even dictate the role, orientations, objectives and actions of other state.
- iii. The policy should be designed to promote, protect and defend a nation's national interests, such as the preservation of national sovereignty, the defense of territorial integrity, the promotion of economic, military, strategic and diplomatic interests; the increase and maintenance of power and prestige, to communicate one's capability to both potential allies and adversaries. Also, to secure and determine the necessary external conditions for the cultural, social-economic as well as political development of her people.
- iv. Foreign policy must rest upon conceptions of aims and objectives.

Background to Nigerian Foreign Policy

The evolution of Nigeria's foreign policy could be divided into two periods, namely the colonial period and the post-colonial period. The colonial period is when the entity called Nigeria came into existence between 1914 and 1960, when the country was still under the colonial rule of the British government, while the post-colonial period is from independence till date. From 1914 to the later part of 1960, the interest of the British was the interest of the entity called Nigeria. Not just Nigeria, other countries of the Commonwealth were content to leave the diplomatic representation of their interests to Her Majesty's government in the United Kingdom. According to Ayah (1998: 27), "In these countries, the interests of all members of the Commonwealth are therefore watched over and protected by Her Majesty's Ambassador or Minister for the United Kingdom. During the colonial period, *Nigeria's external affairs were fully in the hands of the British Governor-General of Nigeria. External affairs were among the subjects reserved for the Governor-General, a Briton.*

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Accordingly, after independence, the post-independence period saw the formation of a truly indigenous foreign policy that was truly called Nigerian foreign policy. With the coming of successive governments since independence, the policy has been mortified. Even though there have been changes in foreign policy formulation by various governments since independence in 1960, the objective of the country's foreign policy still remains the same. Anyaele (2005) posits that the protection of national interests has remained permanent in Nigeria's foreign policy, but the strategy for such protection has varied from one regime to another. This means that all the governments from independence till date have pursued the same goal and objective using different instruments.

From the administration of Sir Balewa in the First Republic to the present administration, the objectives of Nigerian foreign policy have remained the same. It is not wrong to state that the evolution of Nigeria's foreign policy can be traced to when the country gained her independence as a sovereign state. Upon gaining independence in 1960, Nigeria made the liberation of Africa the centrepiece of her foreign policy and played a leading role in the fight against the apartheid regime in South Africa (Samora, 1979). Samora further stated that Nigeria's foreign policy was tested in the 1970s after the country emerged united from civil war and quickly committed herself to the liberation struggles going on in the Southern African sub-region. As noted earlier, Nigeria's foreign policy before independence in 1960 was tied to the interests of the British. When the country gained independence, the first major task the Balewa administration had to deal with was shaping Nigeria's foreign policy in alignment with Nigeria's national interests.

Nigeria's post-independence foreign policy was centered around the Prime Minister, who dominated the foreign policy machinery. He conducted a conservative foreign policy that was pro-West, even though he professed a policy of non-alignment. While he maintained a good relationship with the West, represented by the United States of America and Britain, he was hostile to the Eastern Bloc, represented by the Soviet Union. It was observed that on most international issues, like the Berlin crisis of 1962, the American nuclear test of 1962, and the Vietnam conflict, the Prime Minister leaned towards the West. The only exception was Nigeria's decision to break diplomatic ties with France in protest of nuclear tests carried out by France in the Sahara. When Tafawa

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Balewa assumed office as the first Prime Minister of independent Nigeria in 1960, he outlined what Asogwa (2009) called “broad principles” of Nigeria's foreign policy. The fundamental principles of Nigeria's foreign policy under Tafawa Balewa, according to Asogwa (2009), are:

- i. Pursuance of the policy of neutrality and non-alignment
- ii. Respect for the sovereign equality of all nations
- iii. Promotion of friendship and cooperation among the various countries in the world
- iv. Maintenance of the principles of non-interference and non-aggression in other countries of the world
- v. Promotion of the rapid de-colonisation of Africa
- vi. Maintaining a modest approach to the pursuit of Nigeria's foreign policy
- vii. Support for a free and democratic world
- viii. Promotion and support of cooperation and integration among African states (Asogwa, 2009: 78)

Nigeria's afrocentric foreign policy under Prime Minister Balewa was not in doubt. Balewa was committed to the decolonisation of Africa and the wellbeing of Africans. Under Balewa, Nigeria played a leading role in the formation of the Organisation of African Unity (now the African Union) and the Chad Basin Commission in 1964. Nigeria also contributed substantially to the special fund of the OAU liberation committee and played an active role in the expulsion of apartheid South Africa from the Commonwealth of Nations in 1961. Nigeria's African-centered foreign policy was reiterated by Tafawa Balewa in his speech at the United Nations on October 8, 1960, a few days after Nigeria's independence. In his speech, Balewa informed his audience thus: *So far,*

I have concentrated on the problems of Africa. Please do not think that we are not interested in the problems of the rest of the world; we are intensely interested in them and hope to be allowed to assist in finding solutions to them through this organisation, but being humans, we are naturally concerned first with what affects our immediate neighbourhood (Tafawa Balewa's speech at the UN, Oct. 8, 1960).

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He frowned at the West and East bloc nations using Africa as a battlefield for ideological wars. This came on the heels of the Congo crisis. He was of the opinion that African nations are capable of playing their required roles in the comity of nations only when the developed and industrialised nations stop fermenting crises in African states on the basis of ideology (Asogwa, 2009). *However*, it is instructive to note that the evolution of Nigeria's foreign policy as an independent sovereign nation, dates back to Balewa's administration in 1960. It can therefore be stated that Prime Minister Tafawa Balewa set the principles of Nigeria's policy, which has served as the compass for successive Nigerian governments, even though he recorded minimal success.

Theoretical Framework

To give this work a scientific base, the researchers adopted a realism approach as a theoretical framework. Accordingly, the core thinkers of realism were Thucydides, Nicollo Machiavelli, and Thomas Hobbes. They were followed in the 20th century by Hans Morgenthau, Schelling, and others. Neo-realism is represented by Kenneth Waltz, Mearsheimer, Henry Kissinger, and Raymond Aron, among others.

The theory is based on four key assumptions. First, states are the principal or most important actors. States represent the key unit of analysis, whether one is dealing with ancient Greek city-states or modern state structures. The study of international relations is the study of relations among these units. Multinational corporations, terrorist groups, and other translational and international organisations are frequently acknowledged by realists, but the position of these non-state actors is always of lesser importance. The states are the dominant actors.

Second, the state is viewed as a unitary actor. For purposes of analysis, realists viewed the state as being encapsulated by a metaphorical hard shell. A country faces the outside world as an integrated unit. A common assumption associated with realist thought is that political differences within the state are ultimately resolved authoritatively, such that the government of the state speaks with one voice for the state as a whole.

Third, given this emphasis on the unitary state as an actor, realists usually make the further assumption that the state is essentially a rational actor. A rational foreign policy decision-making process would include a statement of objectives, consideration of all visible alternatives in terms of existing capabilities available to the state, the

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relative likelihood of the alternatives under consideration, and the benefits or costs associated with each alternative. As a practical matter, the realists are aware of the difficulties in viewing the state as a rational actor. Governmental decision-makers may not have all the factual information or knowledge of cause and effect; they need to make value-maximising decisions.

Fourth, realists assume that, within the hierarchy of international issues, national security usually tops the list. A realist focuses on actual or potential conflict between states actors, examining how international stability is attained or maintained, how it breaks down, the utility of force as a means to resolve disputes, and the prevention of the violation of territorial integrity. Power, therefore, is a key concept. To realists, military security or strategic issues are sometimes referred to as high politics, whereas economic and social issues are viewed as low politics.

Challenges of Nigerian Foreign Policy in a Globalising World

Nigeria's foreign policy practice is challenged by professional deficiencies. Sadly, the institutional framework for foreign policy formulation and execution, particularly with regards to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in Nigeria, faces teething challenges. One of the challenges facing the ministry is that of internet connection with the outside world, including its missions abroad, and that *the lifts in the building were not functioning* (Mustapha 2008). Embassy buildings in Khartoum, Teheran, and others in Latin America were said to be leaking. This sort of context is hardly conducive for creative and professional thinking. Accordingly, staffing, training, and funding combine as formidable challenges that glare at the professional practices of Nigeria's foreign policy. This is debilitating to the overall output of foreign policy in Nigeria. Nigeria's foreign policy practice is challenged by professional deficiencies. This is especially so when viewed against the backdrop of the fact that diplomacy is a noble profession requiring a sound intellectual background and a solid grasp of international affairs, *inter alia*. Evidence has it that Nigerian diplomats and foreign policy practitioners seem not to have received the requisite training and orientation to meet up with the diplomatic realities and challenges of the present global age (Fawowara 2008).

Moreover, the Foreign Service Academy, which was established in the early 1980s, only served the training needs of staff newly recruited into the service. There was no systematic programme for follow-up training for this or, indeed, any other category

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of foreign affairs officers (Gambari 1989). Also, budgetary allocations for foreign affairs have always been low to meet the expected service delivery. The foreign affairs ministry receives just about one percent of the federal government budget for recurrent expenditures. In contrast, defence and some other ministries receive far more. More so, the federal character principle in the appointment and placement of persons in positions of importance in Nigeria's Foreign Service has demonstrably undermined merit, talent, and efficiency. Evidentially, the constitutional provision for reflecting federal character and regional balance in the recruitment and appointment of public officers has not served the foreign ministry well. This is due more to abuse of the recruitment process than the availability of well-qualified candidates across the various states of the federation.

The present recruitment pattern, which brings a significant number of ill-qualified personnel into the professional cadre of the Foreign Service, simply justifies the federal character provisions for recruitment into the Foreign Service. In consequence, and more often than not, officers with proven capacity for high standards of performance, innovative thinking, creative solutions, and proactive approaches to policy execution are passed over in appointments and promotions. On the other hand, mediocrity and incompetence are blindly rewarded, while misconduct and unprofessional behaviours thrive under a culture of impunity. Added to this, the phenomenon of appointing and posting a disproportionate number of non-career diplomats to sensitive diplomatic posts is another unfortunate development that is eroding professionalism.

Legislative-Executive Relations

Another challenge Nigeria's foreign policy faces is the difficulty in the relationship between the executive and legislative arms of government. Besides the difficulty in getting the Ministry of Foreign Affairs' budget approved by the National Assembly, ambassadorial nominees also have to be confirmed by the Assembly. In the routine conduct of foreign affairs, the foreign affairs department and officials encounter hitches with the legislature. This organ of the government oftentimes injects itself directly into the foreign policy implementation process. In many instances, the legislative organ of the government reacts to or deals with aspects of Nigeria's foreign relations without the benefit of institutional knowledge and information about best practices and processes. The net effect of this policy of incoherence is that this organ of state then works at cross

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purposes, making Nigeria's foreign policy goals and objectives unclear and ambiguous (Sule 2013: 4).

Opinion and Citizen Involvement in Foreign Policy

The centrality and fundamentality of public opinion in foreign policy processes are not in dispute (Chuka, 2007). Ideally, public opinion inputs and impacts a country's foreign policy determination (Rourke 1997). Especially in democracies, the assumption is that the chance of a foreign policy process is enhanced by public opinion. But since Nigeria's independence in 1960, a number of test cases exist that point to the contrary. Abounding evidence has it that foreign policy decisions in Nigeria are *personalistic*, with the political class acting as independent actors and having free and unfettered hands in policy-making. A number of developments and incidents have shown up to demonstrate the failed and foiled attempts by the public opinion of the Nigerian public to exert influence on the foreign policy process and foreign policy stances of the government.

Articulation of National Interests

National interest is at the heart of foreign policy. Foreign policy is essentially about the protection and advancement of the national interest of a country and, therefore, cannot be operated in a vacuum. Every nation's foreign policy is or should be in the service of its national interest (Eze 2010). Worrisome enough, this centrally important 'National Interest' has defied a comprehensive, clear, and precise definition in Nigeria's constitutions and in Nigeria's foreign policy practices. Analysts and leaders alike are not agreed on what constitutes Nigeria's national interest. Alluding to this, Professor Osita Eze wrote, "It is difficult to identify Nigeria's conception of national interest since independence" (Eze, 2010:81). If it is difficult to define what the national interest of Nigeria is, it will even be more difficult to redefine it in order to provide, among other things, the mechanism and strategy that will facilitate the pursuit of foreign policy to achieve its national objectives, especially given the deepening of globalisation and the emergence of new powerful actors. By every parameter of measurement and consideration, this is a fundamental challenge that confronts Nigeria in the 21st century.

Accordingly, it is noticeable that trends in Nigeria's foreign policy indicating its national interest have not been very stable over time. During the Tafawa Balewa administration, identifiable national interests and foreign policy goals were

decolonization from colonial racists' settler regimes, pan-African solidarity, national economic development, and world peace. Yet under Babangida at the All-Nigerian Conference on Foreign Policy in 1986, he conceived of national interest as simply national security (Agreen 2013). Often times in Nigeria, the adjudged national interest lacks '*nationalness*' and its '*nationalistic*' quality is in great doubt. While the first term interrogates the extent of the people's input and participation in determining what is tagged as their collective interest, the second doubts the people-centeredness of the so-called interests. Viewed from the Marxian perspective, Nigeria's national interest cannot be sequestered from the ruling class. Therefore, according to this school, national interest is another name for the interest of the class ruling at a given time and period in the country. Akin to the above is the challenge of *primordialism* and a lack of tradition in Nigeria's foreign policy process and practice. Excessive personalisation of the foreign policy process by successive heads of state is a huge obstacle to Nigeria's foreign policy progress. The foreign policy of Nigeria during the Tafawa Balewa era was but a reflection of Balewa's personality and character rather than that of the Nigerian state. The idiosyncratic traits of Presidents Murtala Mohammed and Olusegun Obasanjo were the reason for the injection of activism and dynamism into the foreign policy manifestations of the country at the time. With this, Nigeria's foreign policy seems to have been void of tradition. The patterns and processes of foreign policy in Nigeria do change with changing leaderships and regimes. The fundamental question this raises is whether there is really anything like 'Nigeria's Foreign Policy?' Does Nigeria actually own a policy? Will it not be more appropriate to say Balewa's policy, Obasanjo's policy, etc., among others?

Challenges of Afrocentricism

Arising from the afrocentric character of Nigeria's foreign policy are lots of problems and challenges. For some obvious reasons, Nigeria, since her independence, has made Africa the major plank of her foreign policy. For this, Nigeria has supported Africa's course in many respects and participated in various peacekeeping operations. This involvement of the country in peace operations in many troubled African zones has drained both the material and human resources of Nigeria. It has also created conflicting perceptions among different actors in the conflicts, which are carried along in other forums and international platforms.

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More so, Nigerian citizens themselves need to see the practical results and gains of the country's afrocentric diplomacy in the material improvement of their lives; otherwise, they will see no justification for the money spent on these pursuits. Moreso, the age-long grasp of Afro-centrism by Nigeria's foreign policy is long overdue to give way to citizen centrism as a foreign policy stance of the country. Nigeria has for many years pursued, without gain, the good and wellbeing of other African nations at the expense of the wellbeing of its own citizens. The impression that has been ingrained in the minds of Nigerians, especially those living outside the shores of the country, is that the Nigerian state does not care about the plight of its citizens abroad.

Cases involving Nigerians abroad that the intervention of the Nigerian state through the missions would have ameliorated were perceived to have been left unattended. Nigerians who are facing difficulties abroad are almost always seen as sheep without shepherds, yet the constitution unambiguously provides that sovereignty belongs to the people, from whom the government derives its power. It is for this understanding that the government of Yar'Adua began giving thought to what its Foreign Affairs Minister, Ojo Mmaduekwe, called Citizen Diplomacy. This principle, in consonance with the constitutional directive principles, places the priority of Nigeria's foreign policy on the protection of the interests of Nigerian citizens, both at home and abroad. Especially since the post-Cold War era, it has been the expectation that there should be an alteration and shift in the Africa-centeredness of Nigeria's foreign policy in view of the Nigeria's domestic situation and the realities of the post-Cold War international system. It is absurd to rely on foreign policy tools and conceptual frameworks developed in the 1960s for dealing with the modern complexities of an international system, increasingly driven by the forces of globalization. In the era of globalisation, Nigeria has no choice but to adjust and adapt in the way she conducts her foreign policy. For instance, such challenges as climate change, terrorism, and transnational crime issues are impossible to ignore, and imperatively, they reflect on foreign policy formulation and governance at the domestic level. Accordingly, Nigeria's foreign policy must keep a watchful brief on these issues and pay attention to their wider ramifications.

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Economy

The weak state and appendage nature of Nigeria's economy have debilitated the ability of Nigeria's foreign policy to protect the national interest and project it effectively into the outside world. It is a truism that a state's foreign rating and influence, in a very fundamental sense, are a reflection of the health and size of the country's economy. While Nigeria has a large economy, it also has a serious economic crisis that makes it difficult to realise its full potential. The economy of Nigeria exhibits largely a neo-colonial structure, depending on the export of primary goods and the importation of finished commodities. More so, Nigeria is heavily indebted. This, unarguably, disallows her to play the critical roles she craves for in the international system.

Connected to the issue of the economy in Nigeria's foreign policy challenges is the challenge of globalisation. The global transition to the 21st century poses serious challenges to Nigeria, especially in the context of Africa. The phenomenon of globalisation is the singular most profound change in the 21st century. Globalisation refers to the relative liberalisation and homogenization of the globe as a result of the technological revolutions. The focus of this is the advancement in information and communication technology. This has made the transmission of information around the world very easy, fast, and cheap. Today, the world is witnessing extensive global trade patterns that provide greater variety and quality of goods to consumers.

Paradoxically, while globalisation tends to sweep away all barriers to the formation of a single world market, increase the volume of trade, and expand the parameters of consumption, the reaction of nation-states has been protectionist in the main (Mbachu 2009). Presently, there is no country in the world that is totally independent of others. Finance, capital, labour, and goods are highly mobile, as the world has rapidly shrunk as a result of the information age. However, this interdependence poses a threat to developing countries like Nigeria, as it is not equally beneficial to all states because the developed countries enjoy a favourable balance of trade and more economic power than the developing countries like Nigeria. This situation makes Nigeria and other developing countries vulnerable to manipulation by industrialised countries.

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Terrorism

Terrorism is another important foreign policy challenge for Nigeria. In international relations, states have a monopoly over the use of coercive force. In a situation whereby there are non-governmental groups contending with the state in the use of coercive force, a situation of order and counter order ensues; hence, disorderliness assumes the defining characteristic of the state in question. Boko Haram terrorist incidences in Nigeria are too obvious to detain us here. One challenge of this development, especially as it lingers, is creating an impression of a weak government that does not have the capacity to maintain internal security. This, again, can send wrong signals to foreign tourists and investors, especially where the economic diplomacy of the government is anchored on the attraction of foreign direct investments, deepening of trade, and enhancing domestic productivity.

Furthermore, other challenges confronting Nigeria's foreign policy in achieving national interest are the communication gaps existing between the general public and policymakers. In Nigeria, most of the time, the public is not carried along in policy formulation; this, in turn, makes it difficult for the public to appreciate the enormity of government efforts in using foreign policy as an instrument of nation-building. In some cases, it is generally presumed that Nigeria's foreign policy does not capture the interest of the nation but the interest of a few elites in a particular regime. Furthermore, non-coordination of public policies also constitutes a challenge to the effective implementation of the nation's foreign policy. Sadly, most institutions of government in Nigeria, especially foreign affairs and policy-making institutions, work towards achieving the same objectives, but they do this independent of one another, which often makes them work against one another. This leads to a situation where many foreign policy institutions and actors work in opposite directions for the same purpose. Also, embezzlement and mismanagement of public funds are identified as other major challenges militating against the realisation of Nigeria's national interest. Public offices have always been seen by Nigerian leaders as an arena for amassing wealth and not an arena for patriotic service to the nation. It is against this background that this paper seeks to examine the challenges of national interest in Nigeria's foreign policy.

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Conclusion

The discussion on the concept matter was divided into two parts, namely the pre-independence (colonial) and post-independence (post-colonial) periods. During the pre-independence period, i.e., 1914–1960, Nigeria was still under the colonial rule of the British government, and the interest of the British was the interest of Nigeria. In other words, Nigeria's pre-independence foreign policy was controlled by the British to serve their interests. Post-independence Nigeria witnessed the formation of a truly indigenous foreign policy that was truly called Nigerian foreign policy. It is not wrong, therefore, to state that the evolution of Nigeria's foreign policy can be traced to when the country gained her independence as a sovereign state. Nigeria's foreign policy since independence has been pursued within the framework that ensures that Africa remains the natural habitat in which Nigeria can exercise direct influence in the pursuit of her national goals and objectives. It is evident that since independence, Nigeria has aspired to occupy the centre stage of African affairs, using her resources, influence, and power to achieve this aspiration and further her national interests, especially in the West African sub-region. In Nigeria's existence as a sovereign state, the influence the country wields through the instrumentality of foreign policy, which seeks to promote and protect her national interests, can better be assessed within the context of regional and continental leadership aspirations. In the implementation of her foreign policy, Nigeria adopted five principles. These principles are: (i) the policy of non-alignment, which rejects formal military alliances with the capitalist West or the communist East; (ii) the principle of legal equality of states, which is aimed at protecting the small and underdeveloped states; (iii) the principle of non-interference in the domestic affairs of other states; (iv) the principle of multilateralism, i.e., membership in international organizations; and (iv) Africa as the centrepiece of Nigeria's foreign policy. Both internal and external factors have consistently influenced Nigeria's foreign policy. These factors have played some considerable roles in the determination of Nigeria's relations with the international community.

Recommendations

Base on the above stated challenges, the paper recommended the following:

- i. There is a need for Nigeria to adopt a sound economic policy as a fundamental pre-requisite for conducting effective foreign policy. Since all foreign policies spring

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from the economic base of a state, Nigeria's economic base should be re-orientated in such a manner that the country's dependency structure would be removed and a national economy that is capable of sustaining a realistic foreign policy goal be built.

- ii. The need to de-personalize Nigeria's foreign policy is urgent. Expectedly, the leaders' ideas should not be eschewed, but these should be made to pass through distilling process of the decision-making machinery of the state. This calls for the democratisation of the foreign policy-making process, allowing citizen participation and input in the foreign policy processes, and ensuring that the institutions that are constitutionally empowered to take part in decision making are free to play their statutory roles.
- iii. It is of great importance to strengthen the Ministry of Foreign Affairs with adequate staffing, funding, and direction. In order to move forward, the Ministry should be freed from those who from the outside exercise authority over the ministry without taking responsibility for their shortcomings. The Foreign Affairs Ministry should be allowed to take charge of the formulation and execution of Nigeria's foreign policy, and to take credit or blame for its failures and successes. The policy of influx of non-career ambassadors in the country's foreign policy practice is demoralising to the career Foreign Service officers, a good number of whom are denied their rightful aspirations to become ambassadors. This way, the wealth of experiences of the trained career diplomats are emptied to Nigeria's Foreign Service operations.
- iv. There is need to make prominent reciprocity in the delivery of Nigeria's relations with other nations. Elsewhere, foreign policies are based on reciprocity. Nigeria's past experiences in Africa does not bear this out. The idea of accepting the maltreatment of Nigerians by so called friendly nations without reciprocating such actions should be over by now. The policy of 'father Christmas' and 'Free Breakfast' in Nigeria's African policy should be minimized.

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- v. Nigeria's foreign policy should be on *quid pro quo* basis. Government should ensure that the era of grants-in-aid and interest free loans to African countries without any economic or political strings attached is over.

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